

MaxThrust: A Novel, Traveling Wave, Magnetically Coupled , Thrust Motor/Pump.
Max Artusy PhD.

Abstract: A pump is described that has many unusual features. It is driven by a magnetically coupled, traveling wave of electro-magnets, and is a one stroke motor. There is no penetration of the water barrier.

A novel pump having a number of remarkable features, is described. It has been shown feasible by prototype construction.

Background: This device evolved from watching a stingray swim in a tank. A traveling wave in the ray body propels the ray along. Now much loss is due to the lateral component of flow from the ray's propulsion system. Here the traveling wave is developed by an impeller that is confined to a square conduit, This makes all the thrust flow to the rear, similar to a wing flying in its ground effect. This is similar to an Ekranoplan of Soviet design. One can alternately think of this as a fish swimming in a tight channel.

Operation: An impeller or "fish" rides in a rectangular channel, and is driven side to side by the traveling magnetic field. The impeller has a magnetic surface (galvanized iron), but the core is filled with silicone potting for less weight. The arcs of the fish are sections of an ellipse, and are designed as shown in Fig 1.

The impeller rocks along the side wall. When it has reached a complete half rock cycle (magnets 1-6 fired), the opposite side of the impeller is presented to the magnetic field of the opposite side. Then magnet 7 is fired, and the fish is rocked down the opposite side of the flooded channel. Magnets 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12 firing in sequence, one at a time. By design, the fish is set to just be tangent to the opposite side (no gap) as the transfer side to side, is made. This maximizes force at the transfer. Only one magnet at a time is energized, with a square pulse drive.

Fig 1

Pumping action occurs because water is squeezed to the rear , as the magnets sequentially fire (1-6 sequence). At the same time, water is loading on the opposite side of the pump, preparing for the next rearward ejection. We see that for each 1/2 rock cycle down a side, water is ejected. Moreover the opposite side is loaded with fluid. For each traverse of a side, water is ejected. This means the device is

a 1 stroke motor, much more efficient than a 4 stroke motor. Note there is no penetration of the liquid barrier, and that improves reliability.

Electrical drive and field considerations: The magnets produce a traveling wave attractive force on the fish surface, causing it to rock down the side of the channel. Only one magnet is energized at a time. So the coil heating is minimal and allows for the coil to cool between pulses. In this prototype case, the magnets are in air. On a heavily loaded thruster, the coils could be liquid cooled for increased drive. One could also provide energy recovery for the magnet field, and improve efficiency. It can be shown that the force on the gaped magnet pole face when energized, goes as B^2 . This is very important. As the gap is reduced, the force goes up rapidly. $\frac{1}{2}$ the gap produces 4 x the force. This will greatly improve throughput of the thruster. Prototype design had a gap of 0.15 inches dictated by the materials available. Even with is, the pump would run at 20 Hz, This is a very impressive performance, considering the big gap.

The device is easily reversible. This is done simply by starting from the opposite end and firing, 6,5,4,3,2,1,12,11,10,9,8,7. This reverses the direction of the magnetic field wave.

Improvements: A simple prototype was built here to show feasibility and identify things needing work. The design used rheoscopic fluid, dyed blue to observe water flow. This works well at slow flow rates. At slow flow it is apparent the flow channels need check valves, as in Fig 2. This prevents back flow, and cross flow between the input sides, as well as output cross flow. At high flow this may not be necessary. The check valves were made of stip plastic, that flexed at the attach points.

Another issue is the fish tends to swim out of the channel to the rear, when running. A flexible long filament was attached well in front of the pump, and front end of the fish. This keeps the impeller centered with respect to the magnets.

4 CHECK VALVE DETAIL

Fig 2

Conclusion: A novel approach to a 1 stroke, magnetically coupled, high efficiency pump/thruster is presented here. There are countless variations. Many linear, and circular variants are possible. In fact, this is the first in a family of related devices.

Appendix: Device picture.

Fig 4
Setup